

Effect of Pollination on Qualitative Characters of Rapeseed (*Brassica campestris* l. Var. *Toria*) Seed in Chitwan, Nepal

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Abstract : An experiment was conducted to study the effect of pollination quality of rapeseed seed in Chitwan during 2012-2013. The experiment was designed in Randomized Complete Block with four replications and five pollination treatments. The rapeseed plots were caged with mosquito nets at 10% flowering except natural pollination. Two-framed colonies of *Apis mellifera* L. and *Apis cerana* F. were introduced separately for pollination, and control plot caged without pollinators. The highest germination percent was observed on *Apis cerana* F. pollinated plot seeds (90.50% germination) and lowest on control plots (42.00% germination) seeds. Similarly, seed test weight of *Apis cerana* F. pollinated plots (3.22 gm/ 1000 seed) and *Apis mellifera* L. pollinated plots (2.93 gm/1000 seed) were and control plots (2.26 gm/ 1000 seed) recorded respectively. However, oil content was recorded highest on pollinated by *Apis cerana* F. (36.1 %) and lowest on control plots (32.8%). This study clearly indicated pollination increases the seed quality of rapeseed and therefore, management of honeybee is necessary for higher quality of rapeseed under Chitwan condition.

Keywords : *apis cerana*, *apis mellifera*, rapeseed pollination, rapeseed quality

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